

Building Archaeology in Support of UNESCO Rural Heritage Projects: The Case of Fortified Church of Viscri (Romania)

I. Burnichioiu^{1,*}, M. L. Moldovan²

¹ “1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, Alba Iulia, Romania, ileana.burnichioiu@uab.ro; ² Politehnica University of Timișoara, Timișoara, Romania, marius.l.moldovan@gmail.com

Topic: T3.1. Studies of historic urban and rural areas

How to cite: Burnichioiu, Ileana & Moldovan, Marius Liviu (2025). Building Archaeology in Support of UNESCO Rural Heritage Projects: The Case of Fortified Church of Viscri (Romania). In C. Mileto, F. Vegas, A. Hueto-Escobar & S. Manzano-Fernández (Eds.) *Earthen and Vernacular Heritage: Conservation, Adaptive Reuse and Urban Regeneration*. September 10th – 12th, 2025, Valencia (Spain). edUPV. <https://doi.org/10.4995/HERITAGE2025.2025.19501>

Abstract

*The multi-ethnic village of Viscri, the subject of numerous projects aimed at regenerating built heritage, traditional crafts, and agricultural practices, has gained considerable prominence in recent years. However, the systematic inventorying of its built heritage values and the rigorous documentation of these in both the field and archives – to support the quality of ongoing projects and create a sustainable archive for the future – are still in their early stages. The fortified medieval church, which is a key landmark of the site and the oldest built core, lacks up-to-date scientific information (both on-site and in print or online publications), with available syntheses dating back to the late 1990s and early 2000s. Between 2020 and 2024, extensive research was conducted by a multidisciplinary team using building archaeology and German *Bauforschung* methodologies. This research has provided more precise and nuanced historical data regarding the evolution of the complex from the 12th century to the present, as well as insights into the historical roles of its spaces and fittings. The primary objective of this paper is to present the synthesis of the new information and discussions, which may be valuable to specialists, the ongoing restoration and regeneration project (which began in 2023), and the general public. Considering the extended duration of the project and the need for continued research and precise documentation, the second objective of this paper is to provide a list of significant open questions that can guide future studies of this case, which is relevant to world heritage.*

Keywords: Transylvania; Viscri fortified church; *bauforschung*; architectural research; dendrocronology

1. Introduction

Viscri is a Transylvanian village, historically inhabited by Saxons, Romanians and Roma people. The origins of the settlement are estimated to date back to the 12th century and are linked to archaeological traces discovered in the area of the fortified church (Figs. 1-3). However, written references to about the fortified church appeared much later, around the year 1400, when the village

of *Alba ecclesia* (i.e. the white church) is mentioned. The few surviving records also note that in 1494, the church received financial aid (“*pro structura ecclesiae Vyskirch*”) in 1494 from the Sibiu Province and town. They also inform us that Viscri was a village of approximately 50 households around the year 1500 (Fabini, 1998). By the 2000s, the majority of Viscri’s Saxon population moved to Germany.

Nevertheless, with the assistance of several foreign experts and prominent Transylvanian Saxons, the few remaining residents of the village successfully undertook numerous regeneration projects that fostered tourism in the area.

Fig. 1 – Aerial view with Viscri (Șuteu, 2024).

Fig. 2 – The fortified church, view from the south (Moldovan, Siffermann, 2024).

During the process of village regeneration, the medieval church was used for liturgical services by the small Evangelical community, while also hosting tourists and small cultural events. Initially, the church and its modest museum underwent minor repairs, primarily to ensure that they continued functionality.

However, certain key areas of the fortified complex remained unused for decades. The research on the monument stagnated until 2020, when the roof truss of the church began to be studied in detail by M. Moldovan and C. Siffermann. At that time, the parish community recognised the pressing need for a conservation and revitalisation project. The new project was undertaken by the MODUL 28 Sibiu architecture office in 2023. It provided the opportunity to not only pursue archaeological research but also to carry out non-invasive and minimally invasive research on the church, the towers, and bastions and segments of the fortification's curtain wall.

2. Objectives

First and foremost, the primary objective of this study was to reassess the construction phases of the fortified church in Viscri and its furnishing with wooden items, drawing on new sources that provide more reliable chronological information (dendrochronological analyses and epigraphy, cross-referenced with archival sources). This information stems from both published and unpublished research reports completed up to 2024. The paper offers a description of the historical components of the complex and a synthesis of the new findings and discussions, which may prove valuable to specialists, the ongoing restoration and regeneration project, and the general public. Given the extended duration of the project and the necessity for continued research and thorough documentation, the second objective of this paper is to highlight significant research gaps and open questions, providing direction for future studies of the Viscri fortified church.

3. Methodology

An in-depth understanding of a complex whose history spans from the Middle Ages to the present day, in a region with very few written records, can only be achieved through extensive multi- and interdisciplinary research. The 2020–2024 research team employed methodologies specific to *Bauforschung* and architectural archaeology, including historiographical research (in German, Hungarian, Romanian), archival and epigraphic research (painted or etched inscriptions, either *in situ* or copied in the archive) (I. Burnichioiu, M. L. Moldovan, F. Mihály, C. A. Siffermann), photogrammetry (M. L. Moldovan, C. A. Siffermann), 3D scanning (C. Șuteu), architectural surveys (M. L. Moldovan, C. A. Siffermann, MODUL 28), geophysical prospecting (M. Stibrányi et al.), archaeology (R. Lupescu), wall studies (L. Kiss), and particularly dendrochronology (Th. Eißing et al. from the Otto Friedrich University of Bamberg; B. Tóth from the Anno Domini Dendrolab in Miercurea Ciuc, RO).

4. Complex description

The fortified complex in Viscri, which dominates the village and covers over 3300 m² (Figs. 1-3), consists of a single-nave church with a western tower. It is positioned in the centre of an enclosure fortified with towers (4) and rectangular bastions (2) that were constructed from stone of varying quality, as well as brick and wood. In the research reports written in Romanian, its major components were given abbreviated names (according to the cardinal points or their functionalities) that we will also employ here: church = C; church tower = T; gate tower = GT; southern tower = ST; western tower = WT; northern tower = NT; southern bastion (that houses the museum) = SB; eastern bastion = EB; i1 = main fortified enclosure that connects the towers and the bastions; Ci1 = the corridor that surrounds the courtyard near the i1 enclosure. GH, which is outside the fortified enclosure, to the south, stands for the fortress guard's former house (Germ. *Burghüterhaus*), and i2 is the outer, lower enclosure (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 – The fortified complex in Viscri. Major components were given abbreviated names (drawing by MODUL 28, after 3D scan by C. Şuteu).

The fortified enclosure can be accessed via a stone staircase between the GT and ST. Near it, at the GT, there is also a wooden gate that, in the past, allowed access for large equipment. At the

end of the 19th century, steps were placed in front of it, making access exclusively pedestrian during community events. The old bells were installed on the top floor of the GT.

To the west, the church has a massive stone tower (T), with a narrow staircase across the walls of the lower levels and a balcony on the upper level. To the north and southeast, the church has an attached sacristy (S) and a room for the organ bellows (O). The walls of the sanctuary and nave feature buttresses of various sizes, with those of the sanctuary connected at the top by arches. The church has three entrances, on the south side of the nave (two on the ground floor and one on the upper level), each of the first two protected by a porch and the third accessed by a covered staircase. The overall appearance of the church reveals its non-uniform construction, reflecting the multiple building phases that occurred from the Middle Ages to the present day.

The upper levels of the WT and NT are not currently accessible because of the severe deterioration of the staircases and floors. From the patrol path of the fortified enclosure only a few vestiges remain, showing that it had been built on wooden corbels. In place of the patrol path, long since dismantled, the corridor called Ci1 stretches from the SB to the GT and houses several ethnographic items that visitors can view. The complex also had a second, lower outer enclosure, i2. Most of it is visible from the south, west, and north parts of the complex. On the southwest, i2 borders the cemetery (Fig. 2), while in the south it is connected to the GH (Fig. 3).

5. The 2020–2024 research results and discussion

5.1. The church

The older archaeological research endeavours, carried out between 1970 and 1971 (Dumitrache 1978; 1981), uncovered two monetary discoveries that were reassessed in the 21st century (Velter, 2002). These coins showed the oldest construction phases of the church in Viscri

date back to the second half of the 12th century rather than the first half. In the second half of the century, a small Romanesque building was erected: a single-nave structure made of masonry, with a semi-circular apse that is still visible in the ground and in the current walls (as a result of the new wall research). Inside, there are three capitals and a fragment of a Romanesque column (as well as the baptismal font, which was created from two such pieces). These cannot yet be precisely correlated with the first church, although their style suggests that they are of the same period. Although there have long been suspicions that the first church could have been a basilica, archaeology (Lupescu, 2024) and geophysics (Stibrányi et al., 2023) have been as yet unable to provide concrete evidence for such a construction.

Fig. 4 – Medieval construction phases of the church (Moldovan, Siffermann, 2023, Fig. 10).

The western or eastern limits of the Romanesque building of the second half of the 12th century, with its semi-circular layout, have not yet been made visible to the public. However, parts of the elevation have already been identified and are visible (as a result of a wall survey) up to 5.25 m in height on the southern sides of the nave and at the triumphal arch. The initial Romanesque church (improperly called “chapel” by a segment of historiography) was extended towards the east somewhere around the year 1300, when a trapezoidal choir was built, enclosed by another apse, in a somewhat semi-circular layout. Subsequently, the western wall of the Romanesque nave was demolished and the liturgical space reached its maximum surface, which it retains today.

Fig. 5 – Dating of the tower and the roof truss of the church. Building stages from 1473 to 2014 and details of the construction technique for the roof truss (Moldovan, Siffermann).

Correlating the archaeological data from the 20th century (Dumitrache 1978; 1981), the decorative masonry data from 2021 and 2023–2024, and the dendrochronology findings from 2021–2023 reveals that construction work in the western part of the nave began only in the second half of the 15th century when the massive western tower was also erected (Figs. 5 & 6), with masonry up to the bell level. Dendrochronological samples analysed in two different laboratories, in 2021 (Bamberg) and 2023 (Miercurea Ciuc), have shown that the wooden parts of the tower originated from trees chopped in 1473 (in the case of elements from different elevations of the tower) (Eißing, 2021) and in 1493/94 (in the case of an element located behind the Gothic portal between the nave and the tower) (Tóth, 2023). Therefore, the church tower is not a 13th-century (donjon) tower, erected separately from the Romanesque church, as had been assumed and repeated numerous times in the scholarly literature.

The medieval church masonry underwent modifications higher on the walls as well. At approximately 4 m above ground level, the apse becomes polygonal. Wall research, as well as the surface irregularities, have revealed that traces of late Gothic ribbed brick vaults remain on the walls of the sanctuary and nave. Atop this structure, the church seems to have been equipped later with a defensive level (a redoubt).

Fig. 6 – Results of the research on the eastern wall of the church tower, facing the church interior old details and the roofs traces (Moldovan and Siffermann, 2023).

In situ contextual data, correlated with the written sources from around the year 1494, indicates that this defensive level could have existed from the end of the 15th century or the beginning of the 16th until, at the latest, the installation of the current roof structure in 1643 (a date determined by the dendrochronological analysis and an inscription on a beam in the attic: *ANO 1643*) (Moldovan & Siffermann, 2021; 2023; 2024) (fig. 5). The oldest pieces of wooden furniture in the church date back to the same century, but to different years, namely, 1650, 1656 and 1694/1696 (Tóth, 2021; Mihály, 2021). Moreover, an inscription from 1670 that remains *in situ* shows that the church tower received a new patrol path; whether the tower's roof truss is from the same period has yet to be determined. In 1715, the church's expense book records the collection of donations for "the repair and renovation of our weakened church, which endangers the lives of its visitors." Two years later, works on the church are indeed documented (Horwath, 1940; Fabini, 1998). This was probably when the church lost its late Gothic

ribbed vaults. We know with certainty that work was carried out on the church roof truss in 1778 (Moldovan & Siffermann, 2021; 2023; 2024). However, the switch to the flat wooden roof probably occurred in 1793, and not in 1743, despite the inscription painted in black on the triumphal arch that is recorded as *MDCCLXXXIII* (Fig. 7). The argument for the later dating is supported by structural evidence at the roof level and a copy of a 19th-century chronicle in the parish archive. In that archival copy, the inscription contains an additional "L": *MDCCLXXXIII* (Moldovan and Siffermann, 2021; 2023; 2024). Overall, the works carried out in the 18th century were more extensive and more urgently necessary than the earlier changes, given the church's state of conservation. The chronology discussed above is complemented by other records of interventions found in archives, furniture bearing painted inscriptions, and dendrochronological analyses that produced the following dates: 1783, 1790, 1794/1795, 1790/1800 (Tóth, 2021; Mihály, 2021).

Fig. 7 – View of the triumphal arch with painted inscription (Burnichioiu, 2023).

The church walls were painted several times from the Middle Ages to the 18th century, as shown by the wall analyses (Kiss, 2023), and old images depict fragments of medieval frescoes (Fig. 8) and a decorative painting with inscriptions typical of the transition towards the Reformation. The research on the interior decoration is still in its incipient stages as the church has been opened permanently to be used for religious services and visits.

Fig. 8 – *Fragment of medieval fresco* (Kiss, 2023).

Nonetheless, we can say that the current appearance of the church interior, with its painted wooden furniture on the first and second levels of the nave, as well as the choir stalls and the organ in the sanctuary, resulted from the extensive renovations the church underwent during the 18th and 19th centuries. The renovations carried out in the early 19th century were connected with an earthquake that had taken place in 1802, as well as to the need to equip the church with an organ (1817). When the roof structure and the attic ceiling were repaired, the Gothic windows of the church were bricked up, and new windows with pointed or circular arches were added. Additionally, a chamber for the organ pipes installed in probably around 1817 was added in the eastern part of the sanctuary and, according to an 1823 inscription, repairs were made to the upper part of the tower.

5.2. The fortified enclosure – *il*

The archaeological research performed in 1970–1971 showed traces of an oval enclosure to the north, west and southwest of the church courtyard that could be contemporaneous with at least two curtain wall segments currently visible in elevations on the southeast and northeast, that have a different thickness than the rest of the *il* enclosure (Fig. 3). They were dated to the 14th century (Dumitrache 1978; 1981), but we believe that this requires further confirmation – in particular, because the dendrochronological analyses from 2023 showed that the oldest samples of wood embedded in the masonry originated from trees that had been felled in 1546 and around 1577.

Moreover, in the southern area of the fortification (in front of the SB), traces of the supports of a patrol path from the 16th century were preserved (Tóth, 2023).

The dendrochronological analyses also showed that the wood used in the SB was chopped in the winter of 1580–1581. The ST, which is next to the SB, contained wood from 1581 too, as well as wood from around 1478. However, the roof trusses of the SB and ST were remade in 1938.

The GT could be older than the ST, judging by its more archaic overall appearance and its small, semi-circular windows on the upper level. Nonetheless, the dendrochronology and the wall epigraphy have proven that several interventions occurred in the 15th–17th centuries. The final major intervention on this tower was made in 1953 on the top floor, the roof structure and the covering, as evidenced by the archival sources and *in situ* inscription.

The inscriptions in the plaster, together with the 2023 dendrochronological analyses, demonstrate that the 17th century was highly important for the fortification of the *il* and the organisation of the spaces inside the towers and bastions. Beginning in 1630, the current NT tower was built with three levels by the master builder Johann Hartmann from Lovnic (Leblang). In 1648–1649, the WT was raised with four levels by the masters David Zako, Stephan Schullerus, and Michael Fehlessel. During the same period, the curtain wall segments near the towers were built, where a wooden patrol path functioned. In 1970–1972, the roofs of the WT and NT underwent major repairs, according to archival data.

According to the dendrochronological analyses, the EB was erected during a construction phase after 1560 (Tóth, 2023). However, it has undergone numerous intervention campaigns, including a series of restorations in the 20th century, which require further investigation. The EB must be studied for the sake of both the fortification and the church, given that pieces

dismantled from it (some of them dated to 1643) have been identified in the church's roof truss (Moldovan & Siffermann, 2021; 2023; 2024). Renovations also took place in 1828 (according to an inscription on the eastern wall) and 1891 (identified through dendrochronological analysis). The southern-eastern segment of the enclosure was completely rebuilt in the 1960s, and the upper part of the EB was rebuilt between 1970 and 1971.

5.3. The Ci1 corridor

The dendrochronological dating of a beam from the roof of the corridor attached to the western wall of EB to around the years 1765–1769 (Tóth, 2023), has provided an important reference point for this part of the complex, which housed the villagers' grain storerooms (Fig. 9). The patrol path from the 16th–17th centuries have been dismantled at that period.

Fig. 9 – Historical drawing of the Ci1, with access areas and numbered spaces (displayed in museum).

6. Conclusions

The research conducted between 2020 and 2024, in addition to reassessing and critically integrating twentieth-century studies, has significantly enriched the scientific understanding of the fortified complex in Viscri. In recent years, the investigations carried out in this complex have made substantial progress, surpassing those performed at similar sites in southern Transylvania. The data have been

compiled into a chronological table of the monument, which will be a working tool during the execution phases of the restoration and revitalization project and can be modified and updated as needed.

In conclusion, the ensemble of Viscri began in the second half of the 12th century with the construction of a small Romanesque church. The liturgical space was subsequently expanded both eastward and westward, reaching its maximum size by the second half of the 15th century (rather than the 13th century) when the western tower was erected. The medieval church was taller than its predecessor and included a defensive level. It was painted several times over the centuries, but its current interior appearance dates from the 18th–19th centuries. Originally, an oval enclosure with a somewhat smaller area surrounded the church. The construction campaigns of the 16th–17th centuries brought the il closer to the present structure, which now includes two towers and four bastions. During the 18th and 19th centuries, certain parts of the il lost some of their height and features (such as the parapet walk) and were replaced by the current corridor. Covered by a single-slope roof, the structure housed the villagers' numbered "grain rooms."

New studies must aim to address a series of major historical questions that remain unanswered. Where did the isolated Romanesque carved elements in the church originate? Was there ever a noble residence in Viscri (there are no sources on the subject from the early Middle Ages), or was it merely a multifunctional ecclesiastical complex for communal use? Could the study of the church identify the moment the community converted to the Reformation? When was the cemetery relocated outside the complex? Can we definitively rule out the theory that there was once a medieval basilica? What type of structures existed north of the church nave? What other buildings disappeared from the two courtyards? How can the oldest fortification be dated, and did

it originally have towers? When did it appear? Is the GT a tower that belonged to the first enclosure around the Romanesque church? What were the purposes of the numerous spaces that were built over time?

Aknowledgements

The authors would like to express their gratitude to all those who conducted research in Viscri and provided original information for a comprehensive historical and architectural study of 2023, upon which this paper is also based. They would also like to convey their gratitude to the Evangelical Parish of Viscri for the financial support to the fieldwork and laboratory research.

References

- Arhive of National Institute of Heritage. (n.d.). *File 9853*. Bucharest.
- Burnichioiu, I., & Moldovan, M. (2023). *Ansamblul bisericii fortificate din Viscri. Studiu istorico-architectural*. Alba Iulia.
- Dumitrache, M. (1978). Archäologische und Baugeschichtliche Forschungen in der Repser Gegend. *Forschungen zur Volks- und Landeskunde*, 21(2).
- Dumitrache, M. (1981). Evoluția cetății țărănești de la Viscri, jud. Brașov, în lumina cercetărilor arheologice și de arhitectură. *Cercetări arheologice*, 4.
- EiBing, Th. (2021). *Dendrochronologischer Bericht: Viscri (Weißkirch) in Rumänien Kirchenburg Kirche Westturm (Bohrung vom 19.05.2021 durch Thomas EiBing, Auswertung Thomas EiBing/Susanne Schödel)*. Bamberg.
- Fabini, H. I. (1998). *Atlas der siebenbürgisch-sächsischen Kirchenburgen und Dorfkirchen*. Monumenta und AKSL.
- Horwath, W. (1940). *Siebenbürgisch-sächsische Kirchenburgen*. Honterus.
- Kirchliches Archiv Deutsch-Weißkirch. (1874–1972). *Signatur 165. Akten zur Orts- und Regionalgeschichte: Bericht über die älteren kirchlichen Baudenkmäler, 1874; Signatur 174. Bauarbeiten an der Kirchenburg und Ausgrabungsverzeichnis. 1970 bis 1972.*
- Kiss, L. (2023). *Raport despre cercetarea de parament realizat la biserica evanghelică din Viscri (jud. Brașov)*. Târgu-Mureș.
- Lupescu, R. (2024). *Referat asupra săpăturilor arheologice efectuate la biserica fortificată din Viscri*. Cluj-Napoca.
- Mihály, F. (2021). *Viscrist (Deutschweiskirch, Szászfehéregyháza, județul Brașov). Biserica evanghelică. Studiu pentru componente artistice din lemn*. Sovata.
- Moldovan, M. L., & Siffermann, C. A. (2021). *Bauforschung und Gefügeanalyse am Dachtragwerk der Kirchenburg in Deutsch-Weißkirch/Viscrist, 1–2* [Master's thesis, Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg & Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften Coburg].
- Moldovan, M. L., & Siffermann, C. A. (2023). De la șarpantă la zidărie. Cercetări din anii 2020–2021 privind elevația bisericii fortificate din Viscrist. *Annales Universitatis Apulensis. Series Historica*, 27.
- Moldovan, M. L., & Siffermann, C. A. (2024). *Bauforschung und Gefügeanalyse am Dachtragwerk der Kirchenburg in Deutsch-Weißkirch/Viscrist*. Honterus.
- Stibrányi M., et al. (2024). *Geophysical Survey Report Viscrist Fortified Church*. Munifex.
- Tóth, B. (2021). *Dendrochronologische Untersuchung von Sitzbänken in der evangelischen Kirche zu Deutschweisskirch/Viscrist*. Anno Domini Dendrolab.
- Tóth, B. (2023). *Analiză dendrocronologică. Viscrist. Biserica fortificată evanghelică*. Anno Domini Dendrolab.
- Van der Haegen, H., & Niedermaier P. (1997). *Weisskirch (Deutsch-Weißkirch/Viscrist). Ein siebenbürgisches Dorf im Griff der Zeit*. Instituut voor Sociale en Economische Geografie Katholieke Universiteit.
- Velter, A. M. (2002). *Transilvania în secolele V–XII. Interpretări istorico-politice și economice pe baza descoperirilor monetare din Bazinul Carpatic, secolele V–XII*. Paideia.